

Heterobranch Gastropods from Cuba: the family Cornirostridae (Heterobranchia, Valvatoidea)

Gasterópodos Heterobranquios de Cuba: la familia Cornirostridae (Heterobranchia, Valvatoidea)

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RESUMEN

Se estudian 4 especies de gasterópodos Heterobranquios de la familia Cornirostridae, pertenecientes a los géneros *Cornirostra* Ponder, 1990 y *Tomura* Pilsbry & McGinty, 1946, encontradas en la Isla de Cuba. Dos de ellas, *Cornirostra floridana* Bieler & Mikkelsen, 1998 y *Tomura bicaudata* (Pilsbry & McGinty, 1946) son especies previamente conocidas y otras dos, se describen como nuevas para la ciencia. Se ilustran mediante fotografías al MEB y se aportan datos de batimetría, hábitat y distribución.

ABSTRACT

Four species of Heterobranch gastropods of the family Cornirostridae, belonging to the genera *Cornirostra* Ponder, 1990 and *Tomura* Pilsbry & McGinty, 1946, were found in the island of Cuba and are now studied. Two of them, *Cornirostra floridana* Bieler & Mikkelsen, 1998 and *Tomura bicaudata* (Pilsbry & McGinty, 1946), were previously known and the other two are described as new species. They are illustrated by SEM photographs and data on their bathymetry, habitat and distribution is provided.

INTRODUCTION

The Lower Heterobranchia gastropods, also known as the Allogastropoda, are an informal group of rather specialized and highly-evolved marine gastropod molluscs which include among others the superfamily Valvatoidea Gray, 1840. This superfamily comprises three families of Recent molluscs (Valvatidae Gray, 1840; Cornirostridae Ponder, 1990 and Hyalogyrinidae Warén & Bouchet, 1992) and a family of fossil molluscs (Provalvatidae Bandel, 1991).

PONDER (1990) introduced the family Cornirostridae to include two monotypic genera: *Cornirostra* (based on *C. pellucida*) and *Tomura* (based on *T. bicaudata*). WARÉN, GOFAS & SCHANDER (1993) described a new genus, *Noerrevangia* Warén & Schander, 1993, which is included in Cornirostridae and designated *Noerrevangia fragilis* as the type species of this new genus.

BIELER, BALL & MIKKELSEN (1998) provided a redescription of the family Cornirostridae after a detailed anatomi-

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Tabla I. Comparación de los caracteres morfológicos en las especies estudiadas con otras congénicas.

	<i>Cornirostra pellucida</i>	<i>Cornirostra floridana</i>	<i>Comirostra lenticulata</i>	<i>Tomura bicaudata</i>
Shell spire	115-140°	105-110°		130-140°
Umbilicus	Open, unkeeled	Open, unkeeled	Open, unkeeled	Open, keeled
Maximun size	2.3 mm	2.1 mm	1.35 mm	1.25 mm
PC size	217 µm	108-185 µm	180 µm	165-195 µm
PC coiling	Initial hyperstrophy	Initial hyperstrophy	Initial hyperstrophy	Initial hyperstrophy
PC whorls	1.25	1.20	1.20	1.25
TC whorls	2.75	2.05-2.95	2.5	2.0-2.25
PC II sculpture	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth, initial part with 0-2 spiral ridges
TC sculpture	Smooth	Smooth	Fine growth lines	Smooth

cal and morphological study of specimens collected alive of *Cornirostra floridana*, and its comparison with *Tomura bicaudata* and other known species of the family.

Currently the family Cornirostridae comprises 12 species, placed one in *Noerrevangia*, 2 in *Cornirostra* and 9 in *Tomura*. Among them, *Tomura bicaudata*, *Tomura xenoskenoides* and *Cornirostra floridana* were described from the Central West Atlantic. In the present work four species of heterobranch molluscs are studied from Cuba, two of them being previously known (*C. floridana* and *T. bicaudata*) and two new for science.

The comparison of the morphological characters can be seen in Table I.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The material has been collected either by SCUBA diving or dredgings,

mostly by the third author (RFG). No live specimens were observed.

The shells were photographed with an XL-30 Electronic microscope of the University of Vigo.

Abbreviations used:

ANSP, Academy of Natural Sciences, Philadelphia
 MNCN, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid, Spain
 FLMNH, Florida Museum of Natural History, Gainesville, Florida, USA
 MHNS, Museo de Historia Natural, Santiago de Compostela, Spain
 MNHN, Museum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris, France
 IES, Instituto de Ecología y Sistemática, Havana, Cuba
 CFG, collection of Raúl Fernandez-Garcés
 j, juvenile
 s, shell (adult)
 SEM, Scanning electron micrograph

SYSTEMATIC PART

Subclass HETEROBRANCHIA J.E. Gray, 1840
 Superfamily VALVATOIDEA J.E. Gray, 1840
 Family CORNIROSTRIDAE Ponder, 1990

Table I. Comparison of morphological characters of the studied species with other congeneric.

<i>Tomura yashima</i>	<i>Tomura himeshima</i>	<i>Tomura depressa</i>	<i>Tomura apex truncatus</i>	<i>Tomura xenoskenoides</i>
>140°	>140°	130°		
Open, unkeeled	Open, unkeeled	Callus-filled	Callus-filled	Open, unkeeled
1.5 mm	1.9 mm	1.6 mm	1.8 mm	1.86
180-200 µm	200 µm	150-175 µm	150-180 µm	160 µm
Initial hyperstrophy	Initial hyperstrophy	hyperstrophy	hyperstrophy	Initial hyperstrophy
1.50	1.50	1.7	1.25	0.75
2.0-2.25	2.25	2.0	2.75	3.0
Unknown	Smooth	Smooth	Incremental lines	Smooth
Fine growth lines, very weak spiral threads; with thin transparent periostracum	Rough growth lines, very weak spiral threads; with thick, yellowish periostracum	Occasionally initially with spiral ridges	Fine spiral cordlets more evident on the dorsum and on the base	Fine growth lines

The redescription of the Cornirostridae family in BIELER, BALL & MIKKELSEN (1998) is as follows: "Small (<2.3 mm) valvatoideans with (almost) smooth skeneiform teleoconchs of 2-3 more-or-less convex whorls and simple peristome, and (weakly) sinistral protoconchs coiling around the same axis (this hyperstrophic larval might not be expressed if only protoconch I [embryonic shell] is present, e.g., *Noerrevangia*); snout long, with two tentacle-like oral lobes; radula with 7-9 teeth per row including 2-3 partly overlapping lateral teeth, and rachidian with highly developed lateral support; foot with propodial and metapodial extensions, appearing left anteriorly and posteriorly; single right pallial tentacle; bipectinate, basally attached gill; hermaphroditic reproductive system with cephalic penis".

BIELER ET AL. (1998) wrote: "Extant cornirostrids with their non-descript, skeneiform/valvatiform/vitrinelliform shells can only be confirmed as

members of this family through knowledge of their anatomical features. [...] Attempts to establish a deep fossil record for the family (SCHRÖDER, 1995; BANDEL, 1996) by "connecting-the-dots" between Recent, Cretaceous, Jurassic, and Triassic taxa with similarly non-descript shells should thus be viewed with caution".

One of the main morphological characters which differentiate and characterize the species included in Cornirostridae (except *Noerrevangia fragilis*) is to have a slightly hyperstrophically coiled larval shell. Similarly weakly expressed larval hyperstrophy also occurs in other lower heterobranchs, such as *Xenoskenaea* Warén & Gofas, 1993, Hyalogyrinidae, and Omalogyridae (BIELER ET AL., 1998).

The species of Cornirostridae are astonishingly similar in shell characters to species of Vitrinellidae of the genera *Teinostoma* and *Vitrinella*, but shells can still be distinguished by the hyperstrophy of the larval shell.

Genus *Cornirostra* Ponder, 1990

Cornirostra Ponder, 1990. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 56 (4): 533-555. [Type species by original designation: *Microdiscula pellucida* Laseron, 1954].

Remarks: Only two species have so far been described in this genus: *Cornirostra pellucida* (Laseron, 1954) from

the Indo-West Pacific, and *Cornirostra floridana* Bieler & Mikkelsen, 1998 from the West Atlantic.

Cornirostra floridana Bieler & Mikkelsen, 1998 (Fig. 1)

Cornirostra floridana Bieler & Mikkelsen, 1998. *Malacologia*, 40: 307-313, figs. 1-13. [Type locality: Indian Key Fill, mile marker 79, Middle Florida Keys, bay side (Gulf of Mexico), Monroe County, Florida].

Type material: Holotype in FLMNH (278401) and seven paratypes in FLMNH, ANSP and USNM, not examined.

Other material examined: 6 s, Calicito, Cienfuegos Bay, Cuba, 12 m (CFG); 10 s, Cienfuegos Bay, 12-16 m (MHNS).

Description: Shell small (up to 2.1 mm), transparent, with relatively high spire and rounded periphery, smooth with fine growth lines. Protoconch initially hyperstrophic, later nearly planispiral, with a little more than one spiral whorl, measuring about 180 μ m in maximum diameter and having two well differentiated parts: Protoconch I (embryonic shell) with a reticulated sculptural pattern; Protoconch II (larval shell) smooth, finishing in a labial thickening. Teleoconch with nearly 2 ½ whorls; transparent, smooth with fine growth lines. Base smooth, umbilicate, without umbilical keel or cord; the growth lines penetrate into the inner part of the umbilicus. Aperture oval, external lip and columella sharp, not thickened.

Maximum reported size: 2.1 mm. The largest specimen in the examined material measures 1.96 mm in diameter and 1.52 mm in height.

Habitat: Live-observed specimen among turtle grass (*Thalassia testudinum*) and green algae (*Penicillus cf. dumetosus* and *Halimeda spp.*), in shallow water (0-1 m) at low tide (BIELER ET AL., 1998).

Distribution: USA: Florida Keys (BIELER ET AL., 1998). The known geographic range is extended to Cienfuegos Bay, Cuba.

Remarks: The description follows essentially BIELER ET AL. (1998). *Cornirostra floridana* differs from *Tomura bicaudata* by its smaller spire angle (105°-110° vs 130-140°) and by the absence of the umbilical keel.

Cornirostra lenticulata spec. nov. (Fig. 2)

Type material: Holotype (s) deposited in MNCN (15.05/60047). One paratype (s) in MNHN (25141), one more (j) in IES and two (s and j) in MHNS (100572).

Type locality: Calicito, 22° 07.970' N, 80° 29.824' W, Cienfuegos Bay, Cuba, 8 m, Cuba.

Etymology: The species name refers to the shape of the shell, which resembles a lentil in shape. From the Latin word *lenticulatus*.

Description: Shell of very small size (scarcely 1.4 mm), lenticular, more or less depressed, transparent and almost smooth. Protoconch hyperstrophic, with a little more than one spiral whorl, measuring about 180 μ m in maximum diameter and having two well differentiated parts: Protoconch I (embryonic shell) with a reticulated sculptural pattern;

Protoconch II (larval shell) smooth, finishing in a labial thickening. Teleoconch with nearly 2 ½ whorls; transparent, smooth with fine growth lines. Base smooth, umbilicate, without umbilical keel or cord; the growth lines penetrate the inner part of the umbilicus. Aperture oval, external lip and columella sharp, not thickened.

Figure 1. *Cornirostra floridana* Bieler & Mikkelsen, 1998. A-C: shells, 1.7, 1.9, 1.4 mm in diameter, Calicito, Cienfuegos Bay; D: protoconch of another specimen, same locality.

Figura 1. *Cornirostra floridana* Bieler & Mikkelsen, 1998. A-C: conchas, diámetro 1,7; 1,9; 1,4 mm, Calicito, bahía de Cienfuegos; D: protoconcha de otro ejemplar, misma localidad.

Maximum reported size: holotype is 1.35 mm in maximum diameter.

Habitat: The material studied was found in sediments in a coralline bottom at 30 m depth.

Distribution: Only known from Calicito, Cienfuegos Bay, Cuba, its type locality.

Remarks: Like the holotype (Fig. 2A), some shells have a separation between the end of the teleoconch spire and the previous whorl; probably this may be an occasional character or perhaps present only in very mature shells.

Cornirostra lenticulata spec. nov. has some characters which indicate a rela-

tionship with *C. floridana*, such as: the reticulated sculptural pattern of the larval shell; the diameter of the protoconch; the smooth and transparent teleoconch shell; and the

umbilicus without any keel. However, it may be distinguished from its congeneric species by its lenticular form, more depressed than in *C. floridana*.

Genus *Tomura* Pilsbry & McGinty, 1946

Tomura Pilsbry & McGinty, 1946. *Nautilus*, 60: 15. Type species by monotypy *Vitrinella (Tomura) bicaudata* Pilsbry & McGinty, 1946. Florida.

Remarks: PILSBRY & MCGINTY (1945) figured the crawling animal and shell of the type species. PONDER (1990) described it in some detail after topotypic material. BIELER *ET AL.* (1998) compared *T. bicaudata* with the new species described, *Cornirostra floridana* and gave some information on its localization.

Nine species are presently known in the genus *Tomura*: *T. yashima* Fukuda & Yamashita, 1997 and *T. himeshima* Fukuda & Yamashita, 1997 from Japan; *T. depressa* (Granata-Grillo, 1877) from the Mediterranean Sea and the Atlantic coast of Morocco; *T. abscondita* Rolán & Rubio, 1999, *T. sphaerica* Rolán & Rubio, 2008, and *T. umbilobsessa* Rolán & Rubio, 2008, all from West African coasts; *T. bicaudata*

(Pilsbry & McGinty, 1946) and *Tomura xenoskenoides* Rubio & Rolán, 1998, from the West Atlantic Ocean and *T. aqabaensis* Bandel, 2010, from the Red Sea.

Among the nine known species placed in the genus *Tomura*, five, after examination of their anatomy and radula, were placed in four morphotypes: 1) *T. bicaudata*; 2) *T. depressa* (Granata-Grillo 1877); 3) *T. yashima* Fukuda & Yamashita, 1997 and *T. himeshima* Fukuda & Yamashita, 1997; 4) *T. xenoskenoides*.

The new species of *Tomura* here described belongs to the morphotype of *T. depressa*, characterized by having "the appearance of a miniaturized *Natica* and the umbilicus filled out by a callus".

Tomura bicaudata (Pilsbry & McGinty, 1946) (Fig. 3)

Vitrinella (Tomura) bicaudata Pilsbry & McGinty, 1946. *Nautilus*, 60: 15-16. [Type Locality: Missouri Key, Florida (26.8° N to 12° N; 81.2° W to 74° W)].

Type material: In ANSP. Not examined.

Other material examined: 4 s, Cienfuegos Bay, coralline sand, 12 m; 3 sp, Rancho Luna Beach, 40 m (MHNS).

Description: Shell very small, rather thin, wider than high (H/D: 0.63), globosely depressed, umbilicate, the width of umbilicus contained nearly 5 times in the diameter. The protoconch size is between 150 and 160 μm and it presents 2 well differentiated parts. Protoconch I (embryonic shell), with about $\frac{1}{2}$ whorl and with a granulose pattern, clearly hyperstrophic, partially visible. Protoconch II (larval shell) is hyperstrophic, almost smooth with incremental lines, with $\frac{3}{4}$ whorl, and thickened a short distance from its termination. As a result of

the slightly hyperstrophic coiling of the protoconch, the apex forms a minute depression. Teleoconch with $2\frac{1}{4}$ whorls, separated by an indistinct and shallow suture. Upper surface of whorls smooth, evenly convex. Base convex, becoming a little concave near the strong angle or cord which overhangs the umbilicus. Aperture rounded, only slightly prosocline; outer lip thin; columellar margin very slightly thickened, arcuate. Parietal callus thin.

Maximum reported size: the holotype measures 1.2 mm in diameter and

Figure 2. *Cornirostra lenticulata* spec. nov. A: holotype, 1.35 mm in diameter (MNCN); B: paratype, 1.1 mm (MNHN); C, D: paratypes, 1.2 and 1.05 mm (MHNS), all from Calicito, Cienfuegos Bay, Cuba; E: protoconch of a juvenile paratype, same locality.

Figura 2. *Cornirostra lenticulata* spec. nov. A: holotipo, diámetro 1,35 mm (MNCN); B: paratipo, 1,1 mm (MNHN); C, D: paratipos, 1,2 y 1,05 mm (MHNS), todos de Calicito, Bahía de Cienfuegos; E: protoconcha de un paratipo juvenil, misma localidad.

0.75 mm in height (H/D: 0.63). Maximum reported size: 1.5 mm.

The extremely thin operculum is slightly concave externally, of the multi-spiral type with subcentral nucleus; the spiral figure is indistinct, but somewhat over one whorl is visible.

Habitat: Living under rocks (PILSBRY & MCGINTY, 1946). Depth: 0 m

Distribution: USA: Florida Keys: Lake Surprise and Missouri Key, Monroe County, Florida (BIELER ET AL., 1998; PILSBRY & MCGINTY, 1946)). Colombia (DÍAZ MERLANO & PUYANA HEGEDUS, 1994) and Cienfuegos Bay, Cuba (in the present work).

Remarks: The above description is essentially taken from PILSBRY & MCGINTY (1946: 15-16) except for the details of protoconch added from the material examined herein. After the original description, PILSBRY & MCGINTY (1946) comment: "This is a more elevated shell than *Vitrinella helicoidea* C. B. Adams, with relatively larger aperture and smaller umbilicus. One of us (T.L.M.) took three of these, all with the same cleft tail, and kept them living together. They may be can-

nibalistic, for on the third day the animal of one was gone and on the fourth day only a single specimen remained alive. When the living animal was found last year we thought that it represented a new genus which we called *Tomura* (*Nautilus*, vol. 59, pi. 2, fig. 9). The animal is formed as in *Vitrinella* except that the foot is bifid posteriorly, and the tentacles do not appear to bear any cilia; but the shell has all the characters of the typical section of *Vitrinella*. Pending further studies of many micro-molluscs groups we are holding the status of *Tomura* in suspense, as it could not be recognized by the shell alone".

Tomura bicaudata may be distinguished from the other species of *Tomura* except *T. umbiliobsessa* Rolán & Rubio, 2008, by having an open umbilicus and an umbilical cord like a keel bordering it.

The most similar species is *T. umbiliobsessa*, because both have a similar shape of the aperture and periumbilical keel, but they may be separated because *T. bicaudata* has a smooth shell surface and that of *T. umbiliobsessa* is covered with pits.

Tomura apextruncatus spec. nov. (Fig. 4)

Type material: Holotype in MNCN (15.05/60048).

Other material examined: 2 s, Maria la Gorda, Guanahacabibes, Pinar del Rio, Cuba (broken during the study).

Type locality: Calicito, 22° 07.970' N, 80° 29.824' W, Cienfuegos Bay, Cuba, at -8 m.

Etymology: The specific name (in apposition) alludes to the flat apex of the shell.

Description: Shell very small, a little wider than high (H/D: 0.77), globose, with a rather solid umbilical callus. The protoconch size is between 150 and 180 μ m and presents 2 well differentiated parts. Protoconch I (embryonic shell), with about a half whorl and with a reticulated sculptural pattern, is partially visible. Protoconch II (larval shell) is hyperstrophic, almost smooth with incremental lines, with $\frac{3}{4}$ of whorl, ending in a thick varix. As the protoconch has a near-planispiral coiling the apical aspect of the shell is truncated. Teleoconch with 2 $\frac{3}{4}$ whorls,

separated by an indistinct and shallow suture. Apparently smooth, it shows fine spiral cordlets, more evident on the dorsum and on the base of the shell than in the periphery, where they are scarcely perceptible. Aperture rounded, prosocline; outer lip thin; parietal area almost without a callous coating; arched columella, very widened and reflected, forming a strong umbilical callus.

Maximum reported size: the holotype measures 1.77 mm in diameter and 1.37 mm in height (H/D: 0.77). The material from Maria la Gorda measures

Figure 3. *Tomura bicaudata* (Pilsbry & McGinty, 1946). A-D: shells, 1.35, 1.13, 1.14, 1.00 mm, Cienfuegos Bay, Cuba; E: protoconch of a juvenile specimen, same locality.

Figura 3. Tomura bicaudata (Pilsbry & McGinty, 1946). A-D: conchas, 1,35; 1,13; 1,14; 1,00 mm, bahía de Cienfuegos, Cuba; E: protoconcha de otro ejemplar de la misma localidad.

less than 1.1 mm in diameter and about 0.84 mm in height (H/D: 0.77).

Habitat: The shell from Calicito, Cienfuegos Bay, was dredged in coralline sand bottom at 8 m. Those

from Maria la Gorda were collected in coralline sediments at 30 m in depth.

Distribution: Only known from Calicito, Cienfuegos and Maria la Gorda, Cuba Island.

Figure 4. *Tomura apextruncatus* spec. nov. A, B: holotype, 1.77 mm in diameter, Calicito, Cienfuegos Bay, Cuba (MNCN); C, D: shells, 1.04, 1.05 mm in diameter, María la Gorda, Guanahacabibes, Cuba; E: protoconch of another specimen, same locality.

Figure 4. *Tomura apextruncatus* spec. nov. A, B: holotipo, diámetro 1,77 mm, Calicito, bahía de Cienfuegos, Cuba (MNCN); C, D: conchas, diámetro 1,04 y 1,05 mm, María la Gorda, Guanahacabibes, Cuba; E: protoconcha de otro ejemplar de la misma localidad.

Remarks: *Tomura apextruncatus* spec. nov. may be distinguished from *T. bicaudata* by the round aperture, the lack of periumbilical keel and the umbilicus occluded by a strong callus. It can be

separated from *Tomura xenoskeneoides* by the globular form of the shell, the presence of fine spiral cordlets on the teleoconch and the strong callus which occludes the umbilicus.

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

- BANDEL K. 1996. Some heterostrophic gastropods from Triassic St. Cassian Formation with a discussion on the classification of the Allogastropoda. *Paläontologische Zeitschrift*, 70: 325-365
- BANDEL K. 2010. Valvatiform Gastropoda (Heterostropha and Cazenogastropoda) from the Paratethys Basin compared to living relatives, with description of several new genera and species. *Freiberger Forschungshefte, C 536*, Paläontologie, Stratigraphie, Fazies, 18: 91-155.
- BIELER R., BALL A.D. AND MIKKELSEN P.M. 1998. Marine Valvatoidea comments on anatomy and systematics with descriptions of a new species from Florida (Heterobranchia: Cornirostridae). *Malacologia*, 40: 305-320.
- DÍAZ MERLANO J.H. & PUYANA HEGEDUS M. 1994. *Moluscos del Caribe colombiano*. Colciencias y Fundación Natura, Bogotá, 291 pp., 74 pls.
- PILSBRY H.A. & MCGINTY T.L. 1946. Vitrinellidae of Florida, Part 4. *The Nautilus*, 60: 12-18, pl. 2.
- PONDER W.F., 1990. The anatomy and relationships of a marine valvatoidean (Gastropoda: Heterobranchia). *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 56 (4): 533-555.
- RUBIO F. & ROLÁN E., 1998. Una nueva especie de *Tomura* (Gastropoda, Heterobranchia, Cornirostridae) del Caribe. *Iberus*, 16: 119-123.
- SCHRÖDER M. 1995. Frühontogenetische Schalen jurassischer und unterkretazischer Gastropoden aus Norddeutschland und Polen. *Palaeontographica*, A238 (1-4): 1-95, pl. 1-15.
- WARÉN A., GOFAS S. & SCHANDER C. 1993. Systematic position of three European Heterobranch gastropods. *The Veliger*, 36 (1): 1-15.

